

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D5.3 Installation of the power block

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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermozone tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
PU	Public
μGT	Micro gas-turbine

1. THE POWER BLOCK OF POLYPHEM

The power block of POLYPHEM consists of a combined cycle. The top cycle is a micro gas-turbine (μ GT) of nominal power 60 kWe. It is constructed and supplied by KAEFER. The bottom cycle is an organic Rankine cycle (ORC) of maximum power 37 kWe. It is constructed and supplied by ORCAN Energy.

1.1 INSTALLATION OF THE GT

The GT has been installed and tested in the test facility of KAEFER in Bremen (Germany). This action is reported in the deliverable D2.7 Demonstrator on the factory pre-test of gas turbine package and ORC module, dated 30/08/2022.

The gas turbine is not installed at Themis site, because the solar receiver could not be delivered, as it is reported in the deliverable D5.2 *Manufacturing and installation of the solar receiver*, dated on 11/01/2022.

1.2 INSTALLATION OF THE ORC

In October 2021, CNRS prepared the ground to install the ORC machine on a reinforced basement.

Figure 1: Reinforced basement in concrete at Themis site (France)

The ORC machine was constructed and tested by ORCAN Energy in Germany. It was shipped to France in February 2022 and stored at Themis site until it was installed.

Figure 2: Delivery of ORC power block at Themis site

The ORC machine was finally installed on 21 March 2022.

Figure 3: Installation of the ORC machine at Themis site

Figure 4: The ORC machine is installed on its supporting basement

The thermal oil pipes were installed by the end of March 2022. The load bank and damper supplied by ORCAN Energy were installed and connected to the ORC on 01 April 2022.

Figure 5: Installation of the thermal oil pipes (left) and of the load bank and damper (right)

2. SITUATION ON 31 AUGUST 2022

The Grant Agreement of POLYPHEM ends on 31 August 2022. At this date, the ORC is installed, the piping is finished, the actuators are installed (by-pass valves). The machine is ready to be commissioned by ORCAN and CNRS. The commissioning is scheduled in the week #37 (12-16 Sep 2022).